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THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR ANALYZING THE STABILITY OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC SYSTEMS IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITALIZATION (THE CASE OF THE AGRO-INDUSTRIAL COMPLEX OF THE REPUBLIC OF CRIMEA)

In the context of growing geopolitical instability and intensifying sanctions, the issue of regional economic system sustainability is becoming particularly relevant for the economic security of the Russian Federation. For the Republic of Crimea, whose economy is highly dependent on resort tourism and vulnerable to external shocks, the task of ensuring sustainable development by optimizing its sectoral structure has become a strategic priority. This article provides a comprehensive analysis of the theoretical and methodological foundations for studying the sustainability of regional economic systems, focusing on the agro-

industrial complex of the Republic of Crimea as a key element of the region's economic security. A comprehensive theoretical and methodological platform for analyzing the sustainability of regional economic systems has been developed, integrating traditional approaches of the Soviet economic school with the modern requirements of the digital age. The system of regional economic sustainability factors has been refined and expanded to include a digital component; methodological approaches to resilience assessment have been developed that take into account the specifics of the agro-industrial complex's functioning under sanctions; and the need to adapt mechanisms for spatial economic organization to the requirements of digital transformation has been substantiated.

Keywords: resilience of regional economic systems, resilience factors, sectoral structure, spatial reproduction, distribution of productive forces, Republic of Crimea, economic diversification, agro-industrial complex, digital transformation, economic security, regional development, resilience diagnostics, sanctions restrictions, food security

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